
MARINE BIOPOLYMERS IN DRUG DELIVERY

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Abstract

The development of biocompatible and sustainable drug delivery systems has become a primary focus of pharmaceutical research, seeking to overcome the limitations of synthetic polymers. This monograph explores the emerging role of marine biopolymers sourced from seaweed and marine animals as versatile alternatives for biomedical applications. Due to their unique chemical structures, these materials exhibit exceptional biocompatibility, biodegradability, and low cytotoxicity. This work highlights their diverse mechanisms for controlled drug release. Despite challenges related to compositional variability and industrial scalability, marine biopolymers represent a transformative frontier in the design of next-generation, high-performance, and eco-friendly therapeutic platforms.

Keywords: drug delivery; blue biotechnology; marine biopolymers; biocompatibility

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Introduction

The search for biocompatible and sustainable polymers has intensified in recent years, with marine organisms emerging as a rich source of functional biomaterials [1].

Marine biopolymers are naturally occurring polymers obtained from marine organisms such as seaweed, crustaceans, and molluscs [2]. Owing to the vast biodiversity of marine ecosystems and relatively straightforward extraction processes, these organisms represent a rich source of bioactive materials (Fig. 1). Marine biopolymers are particularly attractive for biomedical applications due to their biocompatibility, biodegradability, bioavailability, stability, and low cytotoxicity [3], [4], [5]. Given the increasing demand for safer and more effective drug delivery platforms, marine-derived biopolymers offer a promising alternative to synthetic carriers.

Figure 1. Classification and chemical structures of representative seaweed and animal-derived biopolymers. The figure was created by the author using BioRender; molecular structures were reproduced from [6].

The term *drug delivery systems* refers to formulations in which an active pharmaceutical ingredient is combined with a suitable carrier, most commonly a polymer, to improve therapeutic performance [7]. Drug delivery systems aim to keep drug levels within the therapeutic window using carriers, mainly polymers, enabling controlled drug release. In addition, specialized systems can deliver the drug to specific

sites, which requires careful selection of the carrier, administration route, and release target [8].

Their ability to stabilize drugs, protect them from degradation, improve bioavailability, and enable controlled or sustained release makes them especially valuable for long-term treatments, including cancer therapy [5]. In addition, marine biopolymers can be engineered to target specific cells or tissues, further improving treatment efficiency.

Although the use of biopolymers as drug carriers is a relatively recent strategy, it has attracted considerable interest across multiple biomedical fields, such as cancer therapy, wound healing, and tissue engineering [2]. Nevertheless, challenges including compositional variability, limited scalability, and regulatory constraints continue to restrict their broader clinical translation [4].

Among marine biopolymers, polysaccharides represent the most extensively used class, either alone or in combination with other biopolymers, as alternatives to synthetic materials in a wide range of biomedical and pharmaceutical applications [9].

Based on their biological origin, marine biopolymers can be broadly classified into seaweed and animal-derived polymers. The following sections provide a characterization of the most relevant and promising compounds within each group for drug delivery applications.

1. Seaweed-Derived Biopolymers

1.1. Alginate

Alginate is a collective term commonly used to describe the salts of alginic acid, however, it may also refer to alginic acid itself and its derivatives. Alginic acid is a structural polysaccharide, present in the cell walls of brown seaweed or some bacteria, where it plays a key role in maintaining flexibility and mechanical integrity [10].

Alginates are anionic polysaccharides, composed of β -D-mannuronic (M) and α -L-guluronic (G) acid units arranged in different block sequences [6]. Owing to their ability to form hydrogels through ionic crosslinking with divalent cations such as Ca^{2+} , that bind to the guluronate blocks of alginate chains, forming junctions described by the

“egg-box” model. This mild and tunable gelation allows encapsulation and controlled release of therapeutic agents [11], [12].

Figure 2. Mechanism of alginate gelation through the "egg-box" assembly. The introduction of Ca^{2+} ions bridges the uronate residues, triggering a sol-gel transition. Adapted from [12].

Additionally, alginates can undergo proton-catalyzed hydrolysis, forming “acid gels” upon hydration through intermolecular interactions that entrap water molecules while permitting their migration, which is critical for controlled drug diffusion [13]. Owing to these characteristics, alginates are widely used in drug delivery systems for the encapsulation and sustained release of bioactive molecules. The ability to fine-tune gel properties through M/G ratio, pH, and ionic composition makes alginate, an exceptionally versatile polymer for designing advanced drug delivery platforms [14]. Furthermore, chemically modified forms, such as sulfated alginate, enhance interactions with growth factors and cationic drugs, enabling prolonged and targeted release [15].

Alginates are commonly used in oral dosage forms, but alginate hydrogels are also employed for localized drug delivery in forms such as beads, microparticles, and nanoparticles, which can enhance bioavailability and reduce drug toxicity [13], [16].

1.2. Carrageenans

Carrageenan, particularly in its kappa form has sulfate groups that confers high charge, allowing interaction with cations like Ca^{2+} and K^+ to form hydrogels. These properties make carrageenans useful as gelling, thickening, and stabilizing agents in pharmaceutical and other industries [5].

Structurally, k-carrageenan (KC) consists of linear D-galactose and D-anhydrogalactose backbones with ester sulfate substitutions. With only one sulfate group per repeating disaccharide, KC undergoes a conformational transition into double helices when in the

presence of divalent ions. This structural reorganization increases the polymer's viscosity and stabilizes its ionic groups, making it a robust candidate for controlled release systems [17].

Carrageenan's mucoadhesive properties make it particularly useful for transmucosal delivery, enhancing drug retention and localized absorption [4].

1.3. Ulvans

Ulvan is the principal biopolymeric component of green seaweed cell walls and is characterized by a highly complex and heterogeneous structure. This polysaccharide is predominantly composed of sulfated rhamnose, xylose, and the uronic acids iduronic and glucuronic, which are organized into α - and β -1,4-linked repeating units [6], [18].

Like other marine-derived polysaccharides, ulvan can also be chemically modified to produce thermostable hydrogels with enhanced functional properties [3].

1.4. Fucoidans

Fucoidans are sulphated polysaccharides predominantly found in brown seaweeds and, to a lesser extent, in marine invertebrates. Structurally, fucoidans are mainly composed of repetitive L-fucose units linked by α -(1 \rightarrow 3) and α -(1 \rightarrow 4) glycosidic bonds, with varying degrees of sulphation and, in some cases, the presence of uronic acids. According to their monosaccharide composition, fucoidans can be classified into three main types: U-fucoidans, which contain glucuronic acid; F-fucoidans, composed exclusively of sulphated fucose residues; and G-fucoidans, which include galactose as an additional sugar component [19].

To improve drug delivery outcomes, fucoidans can be chemically modified to alter their affinity for various pharmaceuticals. Such modifications, which include polymer-polymer blending or functional group substitution, significantly increase drug loading capacity and ensure a more controlled and effective release profile [20].

1.5. Agarose

Agarose is a marine polysaccharide extracted from red algae, structurally related to carrageenans. It consists of alternating galactose residues linked by α -(1 \rightarrow 3) and β -(1 \rightarrow 4) glycosidic bonds in a repeating (AB)_n pattern, differing from carrageenans by the L-conformation of unit A [3].

Agarose readily forms thermoreversible hydrogels and is widely used in the fabrication of particles, microcapsules, microspheres, and hydrogel-based drug delivery systems [21]. However, agarose hydrogels often exhibit an initial burst release, which can be mitigated by structural modifications such as layer-by-layer polymer coatings to achieve more controlled drug release [22].

2. Marine Animal-Derived Biopolymers

2.1. Chitin & Chitosan

Chitin is a highly abundant and renewable marine biopolymer found in the exoskeletons of crustaceans such as crabs and shrimp (also in green algae). Its structure, often associated with calcium carbonate, provides mechanical strength to shells. Through deacetylation, chitin is converted into chitosan, a natural cationic polymer rich in reactive amino groups, which enhances its applicability in biomedical and pharmaceutical fields [6], [23].

Chitin is still largely unutilized because its semi-crystalline structure with a large number of intermolecular hydrogen bonds causes it to be insoluble in most solvents. With the advent of new technologies, however, the partial N-deacetylation of chitin can now be converted into a soluble substance called chitosan [7], [24].

Chitosan, derived from chitin, exhibits strong mucoadhesive properties because of its positive charge, enhancing adhesion to mucosal surfaces and prolonging drug contact time. Regarding its application in drug delivery systems, chitosan is generally eliminated by renal clearance. However, high molecular-weight chitosan requires prior enzymatic degradation before excretion [25].

2.2. Marine Collagen

Marine collagen is an insoluble fibrous structural protein derived from the connective tissues of marine organisms, particularly from fishes, or invertebrate marine animals, such as marine sponges or jellyfish [4], [26]. It belongs to a family of extracellular matrix proteins organized in a hierarchical fibrillar structure, with more than 20 collagen types identified. The triple-helical conformation and the presence of abundant amino groups confer collagen nanoparticles with relatively high surface charge density, promoting interactions with bioactive molecules [26], [27].

Collagen-based nanoparticles have shown promise as carriers for transdermal drug delivery, while the ability of collagen to influence cell adhesion and differentiation makes it attractive for localized and tissue-targeted therapeutic systems [28].

2.3. Marine Gelatin

Gelatin-based bio-inks promote cell adhesion and proliferation, reflecting the biological properties inherited from collagen, from which gelatin is obtained by partial hydrolytic degradation [29], [30]. Owing to its natural origin, gelatin is biocompatible and biodegradable, making it highly suitable for drug delivery applications. Its encapsulation capacity enables controlled drug release, improves pharmaceutical stability, and facilitates targeting of specific sites. Furthermore, gelatin can be processed into diverse carrier systems, including nanoparticles, microparticles, and hydrogels, supporting advances in tissue engineering and personalized medicine [29].

2.4. Marine Keratin

Keratin is a cysteine-rich fibrous protein classified into α - and β -keratins, depending on tissue origin. α -Keratin is predominant in soft tissues such as hair, wool, and skin, whereas β -keratin is mainly found in harder structures like fish scales. Both forms exhibit a filamentous structure, with α -keratin intermediate filaments presenting larger diameters than β -keratin filaments. The high content of disulfide and hydrogen bonds confers keratin excellent mechanical strength, stability, and resistance to proteolytic degradation [31], [32]. Additionally, keratin contains bioactive amino acid sequences such as RGD and LDV, which enable specific binding to integrin receptors

overexpressed in various cancer cells, making keratin a promising biomaterial for cancer-targeted drug delivery [31]. Owing to its biocompatibility, biodegradability, and intrinsic cell-interaction sites, keratin has been processed into scaffolds, hydrogels, and other drug delivery systems [33].

2.5. Hyaluronic Acid

Hyaluronic acid (HA) is a linear anionic polysaccharide belonging to the glycosaminoglycan family, composed of alternating units of N-acetyl-D-glucosamine and D-glucuronic acid linked by β -(1 \rightarrow 3) and β -(1 \rightarrow 4) glycosidic bonds [3]. Although intrinsically biocompatible, native HA lacks sufficient mechanical strength to act as a supportive scaffold, leading to its frequent crosslinking with esters or other biodegradable polymers to enhance stability while preserving bioactivity [21].

In drug delivery systems, HA is widely used as a surface-functionalizing agent for nanocarriers due to its strong affinity for the CD44 receptor, which is overexpressed in many cancer cells, enabling targeted and safer anticancer drug delivery [34], [35].

Marine Biopolymers for Controlled Drug Release

In drug delivery, the choice of polymer is central because it affects key properties such as biocompatibility, biodegradability, mechanical strength, drug loading capacity, and release kinetics. Polymers influence how a drug is protected during circulation, how it interacts with biological tissues, and how it is released at the target site [36].

A comparative overview of the polymers discussed in this work, highlighting their main characteristics and applications in drug delivery systems, is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of the biopolymers addressed, their drug release mechanisms, barrier properties, and primary biomedical functionalities.

Biopolymer	Drug Release Mechanisms	Barrier Properties	Functionalities	References
Alginate	Cation-induced gelation for managing hydrophilic drug flow.	Absorbs fluids and maintains a moist wound environment.	Fluid absorption, ionic crosslinking, and wound care.	[4]

Carrageenan	Ion-dependent gel strength controls the drug escape rate.	High water retention; ideal for mucosal barriers.	Viral/tumor defense and gelling for medical dressings.	[4]
Fucoidan	Electrostatic/covalent binding for targeted bioactive delivery.	Enhances hydration with antioxidant and protective effects.	Immune system enhancement and fibroblast activation.	[4]
Ulvan	Hydrogel-based release via diffusion or matrix breakdown.	Superior moisture retention via sulfate groups; protective.	Hydrogel formation for vaccines and skin recovery.	[4]
Agarose	Hydrogel-based with high porosity, and encapsulation efficiency.	Neutral surface charge in different pH.	Hydrogel formation for the release of bioactive agents	[3], [22]
Chitosan	pH- responsive/ mucoadhesive; TPP-crosslinked for steady release.	Antimicrobial, semi-permeable, and moisture-preserving films.	Mucosal binding, pH-led delivery, and tissue repair.	[4]
Collagen	Fibrillar network that regulates peptide release via diffusion.	Supports hydration and biological scaffold formation.	ECM structural mimicry and blood vessel formation.	[4]
Gelatin	Enzyme-triggered matrix; tunable through various crosslinking.	Enables gas exchange while keeping the site moist.	Film production and thermal-based therapeutic release.	[4]
Keratin	pH- responsive release, and Hydrogels with long acting potential	Antiproliferative activity	Wound healing and tissue regeneration capacity	[31], [33]
Hyaluronic Acid	pH-sensitive, and Crosslinked hydrogels	Exceptional adhesive strength, and minimal cytotoxicity	Reduced oxidative and inflammatory effects	[21]

To transform marine biopolymers into effective drug carriers, they must first be extracted and characterized [8]. Afterward, they can be processed into different drug delivery platforms, such as nanoparticles, microparticles, or hydrogels, using various preparation methods. Common techniques include supercritical fluid extraction, electrospraying, desolvation, spray freeze-drying, layer-by-layer self-assembly, and microemulsion methods [37].

In drug delivery, polymer-based systems can be classified according to their release mechanism: diffusion-controlled devices (monolithic), systems activated by solvents through swelling or osmotic processes, chemically-degradable polymers, and stimuli-responsive devices that respond to external factors such as pH or temperature [38].

Challenges and Future Direction

Marine polymers have gained attention as drug delivery carriers due to their favorable physicochemical properties, biocompatibility, and biodegradability [2]. However, significant challenges remain in translating marine-derived polymeric nanoparticles from laboratory research to industrial production. Scaling up requires improved control over particle size, drug encapsulation efficiency, reproducibility, and the minimization of side effects [1], [4]. In addition, although several marine-derived bioactive compounds with anticancer activity have been patented. Sustainability is a major issue, as marine biopolymers are frequently sourced from region-specific or seasonal organisms, increasing costs and limiting large-scale supply [39].

To address these challenges, regulated use of marine resources and the adoption of mariculture and aquaculture practices are essential to ensure a stable and sustainable supply [39]. Alternatively, synthetic or bioengineered analogues that mimic marine biopolymers offer a promising solution, as they reduce reliance on marine extraction and help protect vulnerable ecosystems [4].

Conclusion

Marine biopolymers derived from seaweed and marine animals constitute a promising class of materials for drug delivery systems due to their biocompatibility, biodegradability, low toxicity, and structural diversity. As highlighted in this review, these materials enable efficient drug encapsulation, controlled release, and, in some cases, targeted delivery, making them particularly attractive for applications such as cancer therapy, wound healing, and tissue engineering.

However, their broader clinical and industrial translation remains limited by challenges including compositional variability, difficulties in standardization, scalability of production processes, and sustainability concerns related to marine resource exploitation. Future advances in this field will rely on improved processing and characterization methods, as well as on the development of synthetic or bioengineered analogues that preserve the functional advantages of marine biopolymers. Overall, interdisciplinary efforts will be essential to fully exploit their potential in safe, effective, and environmentally sustainable drug delivery platforms.

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